

Using bulk oxygen uptake to assess the welfare of adult Atlantic salmon, *Salmo salar*, during commercial live-haul transport

S. Tang ^a, C.J. Brauner ^a, A.P. Farrell ^{a b}

^a Department of Zoology, University of British Columbia, 6270 University Blvd., Vancouver, BC, Canada V6T 1Z4

^b Faculty of Land and Food Systems, University of British Columbia, 2357 Main Mall, UBC, Vancouver, BC, Canada V6T 1Z4

Abstract

Adult Atlantic salmon are routinely live-haul transported at high densities for long periods of time as one of the last intensive processes in a commercial aquaculture operation before fish processing. Therefore, ensuring the welfare of these fish during transport is critical to product quality. As an indirect assessment of fish welfare during transport, flow-through respirometry was used on board a commercial live-haul vessel to measure bulk oxygen uptake rate ($M'O_2$) for large masses of salmon being transported for over 10 h. Bulk $M'O_2$ was 2.98 ± 0.13 mg O₂ min⁻¹ kg⁻¹ after 1 h of transport and decreased to 2.03 ± 0.14 mg O₂ min⁻¹ kg⁻¹ after 10 h of transport. These rates of oxygen uptake were comparable to the routine oxygen uptake rates previously measured in tank-raised adult Atlantic salmon and in individual wild Pacific salmonids using swim-respirometers. Therefore, the values for bulk $M'O_2$ suggest that salmon recovered quickly from any stress of loading and stress was low throughout the 10 h of live-haul, perhaps indicating that salmon welfare was acceptable during the live-haul transport procedures that we followed. Using a mixed effects regression model, we found that bulk $M'O_2$ was positively affected by water temperature, and calculated the temperature coefficient (Q_{10}) to be 1.9–2.0 between 7.8 and 15.0 °C. The model also showed that loading densities between 62 and 150 kg m⁻³ did not significantly affect bulk $M'O_2$.